

Jizzah City Community Centers Scientific Basis of its Formation and Development

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Abstract:

In this article, the specific stages of the development of the city of Jizzakh have been realized and the work that needs to be done has been reviewed, the development of public centers and the establishment of new public centers based on the laws of urban planning have been put forward.

Keywords: City, street, housing, plan, floor, industry, production, town, square, community, population, construction, new, area.

Currently, two options for the development of the city of Jizzakh are proposed, which take into account the current planning situation in the city.

According to the first option, the territorial development of the city is based on the study of the general direction of the previous master plan. It should be taken into account, that is, in the northeastern direction, because of the refusal to include the villages of Jilig'uli and Saykhan in the city limits, these villages are separated from the city limits, especially Saykhan. Appropriate master plans should be developed taking into account the development of the area. At the same time, the inclusion of settlements such as Taqchilik and Koshbarmoq in the city. The analysis of the existing border of the city showed that it is possible to reduce the area of the city due to the partial change of the crossing of the border in the foothills.

In the first regulation, the city area covers an area of 6537.68 hectares, the population is 210.0 thousand people, the housing stock is 4200.0 thousand m², by 2030 the average area for 1 person is 20.0 m².

Territorial development of the city according to the second regulation takes into account the development of the previous master plan. At the same time, it includes settlements located in the northern direction, around the historical place - Ordai.

Thus, as in the first version, Jiliguli and Saykhan villages will not be included in the city limits. The territorial and numerical increase of the city occurs as a result of the addition of such settlements as Taqchilik, Koshbarmoq, Gulama, Pakhtaabad, Ziyokor, Gandumtosh. At the same time, the trend will continue to partially change the border in the foothills.

In the second arrangement, the city occupies an area of 9127.65 hectares, has a population of 260.0 thousand people, a housing stock of 5200.0 thousand m², an average of 20.0 m² per person by 2030.

The second factor is that the settlements located in the northern part of the city are almost united and have a common planning structure. Residents of these villages have been using urban cultural objects for their own purposes for a long time. In addition, by the decision of the government, a number of settlements were moved to urban settlements, that is, in practice, they will develop in the same conditions as the city of Jizzakh.

At the same time, special attention should be paid to the development and expansion of production and industrial areas, and creation of favorable conditions for workers should be provided.

In this way, the territory of the city of Jizzakh expands and becomes a sufficient factor for the development of population and community centers.

Taking into account the scale and nature of the villages that are planned to be added to the city territory, taking into account the estimated population in the future, the city of Jizzakh should be considered and designed as a large city, taking into account the requirements of modern urban planning, the rules and norms of urban planning.

The decision on the expansion and master plan of the city of Jizzakh is based on the following principles:

1. Taking into account the environment adjacent to the city of Jizzakh, complex organization of residential and industrial zones, creation of favorable conditions for work, living and recreation.
2. Organization of convenient traffic and pedestrian routes between the main zones and external roads.
3. Development of architecture and planning construction taking into account the natural conditions and supporting elements of the existing situation, water surfaces, landscaping and utilities.
4. Development of the planned development of the city in order to create an architectural and urban planning complex.

As a result of tasks, the solution of the master plan is reduced as follows.

- For functional use, the city territory is divided into industrial and residential. These zones include two planning areas that form the entire planning structure of the city.
- With developed transport and engineering infrastructure, it allows creating modern residential areas at each stage of urban development, developing the western and northern regions, and integrating separated settlements into a whole.
- Construction of a new sports and park zone, as well as residential centers in the north-east in order to beautify new areas and simplify existing ones.
- By directing transit flows outside the city outskirts, it creates an opportunity to supply the existing part of the city with transport.
- Allows industrial enterprises to develop industrial zones taking into account priority winds and create sanitary protection zones from these objects.

- Based on the lowland of the Sangzor River, it will be possible to create recreation areas with the developed system of water reservoirs.
- Makes it possible to irrigate the city and supply drainage water outside the city.

Planning of the city center. Center organization and architectural-spatial composition. The master plan envisages the further development of the Jizzakh center in two main directions:

- ✓ in the north, towards Orda.
- ✓ in the north-east, towards Uchtepa.

The city center is developing simultaneously with the growth of residential buildings in the northeast direction, in accordance with the general development of the city.

Its structural construction is based on the structure of city highways, which serves as the basis for urban environmental planning, as well as the existing administrative center.

The first planning district of the most importance in this composition is "Zapadniy", which combines its two features, that is, the old part of the city with the architectural-historical monument "Orda" and the part that is developing on the basis of the new dome.

The scale of the regional center, national architectural traditions and modern trends in architecture require intensive use of the territory and the creation of large complexes that include a wide range of functions.

High-rise business buildings and structures should be created in the city center, including various offices, hotels, banquet halls, exhibition halls, lecture halls and clubs.

The centers of population attraction are the markets of the city, they are located in the new part of the city in the Farmer's market district, in the Privokzalni district and in the northern part of the city, Almazor market, which combines the sale of agricultural and clothing products in different areas. There are also a number of small markets in the city that serve the population.

The current state of planning in the city and the tendency to bring housing estates closer together were taken into account when placing the centers of population attraction. In addition, in order to improve the living conditions of the population, in each residential system, regardless of its typology, there are complexes consisting of objects of periodic use for cultural and domestic purposes. All systems of city centers are connected by a single system of green spaces, which includes the city's irrigation system and serves to reduce air temperature on hot days. The landscaping system connects both residential and planning areas with recreation centers located along the city's main sprinkler.

The park areas, which serve as recreation areas for workers, are located in different parts of the city, taking into account the topography and planning environment.

One of them is located in the city of Orda, where the monument is located, and the other is located at the foot of the river. This place is designed for entertainment for adults and children.

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A park has been planned and partially implemented on People's Friendship Avenue, and it is planned to create the central stadium of Jizzakh.

It is necessary to continue the work on filling the children's park with modern attractions and creating a water complex on the river bank.

Taking into account the hot climate of the region, it is necessary to create closed pedestrian streets, use underground stations to place shops in heavy commercial areas, especially in huge bazaars. It

should be noted that the Western planning area occupies a huge area bounded by the highway in the direction of Forish in the west, People's Friendship Avenue in the east, and the ring road highway in the north. , in the south - United Street. There are five residential areas in this area, depending on their location, they fulfill the tasks defined in the previous master plans and are preserved today.

The main streets of this planning area are Sh. the project can be used not only for tourist purposes, but also for providing services to city residents.

There is a "Jizzakh" railway station, which carries out cargo and passenger transportation, and two bus stations in the city:

One is in the north - it serves the northern and north-eastern directions.

The second - the southern route - mainly provides long-distance transport, as well as serving southern local routes.

There are repair, light, food, furniture industry, and industrial building materials production enterprises in the city.

In recent years, many joint, small, private enterprises and firms belonging to various branches of industry have been formed.

The newly built railway station in the city of Jizzakh, the building of the Center for Entrepreneurs, parks, markets, an amphitheater with 3,000 seats added beauty to the city of Jizzakh. The modern "House of Happiness" complex, a stadium for 10,000 spectators, a number of medical and cultural centers, and residences completely changed the appearance of the regional center.

Even today, modern enterprises, communication networks, infrastructure facilities, new schools, lyceums and colleges, sports complexes are being built in the city of Jizzakh, and the city is becoming more beautiful and prosperous day by day. A number of large industrial enterprises, production and service facilities, newly built in the city area, make a great contribution to the socio-economic development of the region. Foreign guests who are satisfied with the fundamental changes in our country are surprised and excited. The urban planning activities in Jizzakh are being carried out taking into account the rich natural heritage.

In order to expand the territory and form public centers, it will be possible to establish a new city center in the area close to the industrial area along the north-eastern direction.

In this regard, in the master plan, it is necessary to establish a new city center, taking into account the general development of the urban environment in the north-eastern direction.

Such regulation allows moving the city to new areas for the purpose of developing the sphere of cultural and public services.

Planning the construction of a community center with various cultural, household and educational facilities, a sports and park complex with indoor gyms and a swimming pool, a complex of sports and recreation facilities, parking lots, as well as recreation facilities for the residents of the region. In part, this center may also serve as the center of the northeastern industrial zone. The housing estates in this part should be equipped with appropriate cultural facilities, placed on the highways serving this area.

The types of planned park areas vary by age, namely; creation of kindergartens, parks for mixed ages, including sports and fitness centers, zoos and botanical gardens.

Planned improvement of urban parks, avenues and transport routes improves the living conditions of people in hot climates.

At the same time, it should be noted that the existing external routes of the street network and urban highways did not always allow to isolate from the harmful effects of the Jizzakh desert and the wind

regime. In this regard, the project will have to adopt a system of green lines along the main street and along the meridional greening boulevards and roundabouts of the city.

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